

REBUILD

Working Paper

The Own Resources Decision (ORD) & EU
public finances

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Abstract:

In the wake of the COVID-19 crisis, followed by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the EU's public finances are undergoing a transformation process, both in terms of expenditures and revenues. The classic Multiannual Financial Framework has been reinforced with a specific additional Fund (Next Generation EU), which represents a significant volume of public spending. Its centrepiece is the Recovery and Resiliency Facility, now amended by the REPowerEU Regulation. To finance this fund the European Commission is borrowing on the capital markets on behalf of the EU. The need to finance this European public debt may well be the definitive impetus for new EU taxes. This tax reform is not easy due to the unanimity rule, among other factors; but it reflects a very important change within the EU, both in its own fiscal policy and that of the states, and it also implies a strategic reconfiguration of the EU, which is yet to be defined.

Keywords: *Next Generation EU; Multiannual Financial Framework; EU Budget; EU's Own Resources; European Public Debt; EU Taxes.*

1. Introduction

The crisis triggered by the Covid-19 pandemic has been addressed by the European Union (EU) under very different fiscal policy parameters than those followed to deal with the euro-crisis starting in 2008.² In response to the economic crisis of 2008, strict budgetary discipline and a significant reduction in public spending were implemented; in contrast, in response to the pandemic, the EU has applied an expansionary fiscal policy. In particular, both EU and national fiscal rules have been suspended (the “general escape clause” has been activated for the first time, although medium- and

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² In this chapter we adopt a concept of *fiscal* policy as an *integrated* policy, both in terms of expenditures and revenues, from the perspective of Public Finance Law.

long-term fiscal sustainability must continue to be ensured), and a Recovery Plan for Europe has been adopted, involving a significant amount of public spending.

This chapter analyses the transformation of the EU's public finances after the pandemic, both in terms of public expenditures and public revenues, particularly focusing on the 2020 EU Own Resources Decision (ORD) and the Commission's proposed package for new own resources in 2021 and 2023.

The chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 explains the context and general features of the post-Covid EU fiscal policy, with particular attention to the suspension and reform of the EU's fiscal rules and the approval of NGEU. Section 3 provides an overview of the RRF and its financing by means of the own resources system. Sections 4 and 5 focus on the transformation of the EU's public finances after the Covid-19 pandemic, both in terms of expenditures and revenues, with particular emphasis on the European public debt and the need to finance the rising costs of EU borrowing through genuine own revenues (new EU taxes). Finally, section 6 concludes.

2. The context and general features of the post-Covid EU fiscal policy

2.1. The suspension and reform of the EU's fiscal rules

Regarding the budgetary discipline rules stemming from the 1997 Stability and Growth Pact (SGP)³, on 20th March 2020, the European Commission activated the “general escape clause” for the first time.⁴ This clause had been introduced in Art. 5.1 of Regulation No. 1466/1997 by the 2011 SGP reform.⁵ This clause allows Member States to temporarily deviate from their budgetary targets in extraordinary circumstances, provided that such temporary deviation does not endanger medium-term fiscal sustainability.

In view of the crisis caused by the Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine, the European Commission has decided to maintain the suspension of the fiscal rules until 31st December 2023.

On 10th February 2024, the Council and European Parliament (EP) reached a provisional political agreement on the proposed reform of the EU's economic governance framework. This agreement is subject to final approval by the Council and the Parliament. Once adopted, the new fiscal rules will enter into force after their publication in the EU's Official Journal. By 20th September 2024, the first national plans will need to be submitted.⁶

³ We are essentially referring to the government deficit and debt criteria (article 126.2 of the TFEU), whose maximum percentages in relation to GDP (3% and 60% respectively) are set out in article 1 of the Protocol (no. 12) annexed to the TFEU on the excessive deficit procedure. In addition to these criteria for government deficit and debt, there is the European expenditure rule, provided for in Article 5 of the Surveillance Regulation.

⁴ Communication from the Commission to the Council on the activation of the general escape clause of the SGP dated 20th March 2020 (COM (2020) 123 final).

⁵ Regulation (EC) No 1466/97 dated 7th July 1997 on the strengthening of the surveillance of budgetary positions and the surveillance and co-ordination of economic policies.

⁶ See Chapter 20 in this book: Lucio Pench, “NGEU & the new Stability & Growth Pact: innovation and continuity in the light of Next Generation EU”.

2.2. The approval of Next Generation EU

In July 2020, to reinforce the classic Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), the European Council agreed on the Commission proposal to set up the NGEU Recovery Fund. This fund was approved by Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 dated 14th December 2020 establishing an EU Recovery Facility to support the recovery from the Covid-19 crisis (referred to as the Next Generation EU – NGEU). NGEU is the largest fiscal stimulus package for Member States ever approved by the EU, totalling €750 billion (at 2018 prices)⁷.

The NGEU is having a significant impact on the main legal and financial institutions of the EU.⁸ We can therefore affirm that we are witnessing a “transformation” of the EU’s public finances. In terms of spending, this is a process that overlaps with the transformation of public expenditures law, which stemmed from the euro-crisis.⁹ The classic MFF has been reinforced with the NGEU, the implementation of which compels Member States to invest in the EU’s strategic priorities and objectives.¹⁰

In order to meet these challenges, new legal and financial instruments are needed, particularly in terms of public revenues. Thus, to finance NGEU, the European Commission, due to the limited EU budget, is borrowing on the capital markets on behalf of the EU, taking on obligations to raise substantial loan revenues. The need to guarantee these loans and help finance the costs of their repayment has led the EU to expand its own resources system in two ways: firstly, by increasing its room for manoeuvre by modifying existing resources; and secondly, by creating a new category of own resources and future resources, some of which are clearly taxes for non-fiscal purposes, in line with the EU's strategic objectives. In order to achieve this, a new Decision on the own resources system has been adopted in 2020, which was ratified by all 27 Member States, and entered into force retroactively on 1st January 2021. In December 2021 and June 2023, the European Commission has proposed the next generation of own resources, as we will see below.

These new legal-financial instruments must be analysed in relation to the instruments already provided for in previous EU legislation, both in terms of expenditures and revenues. Firstly, we will analyse the Recovery and Resilience Facility, as the centrepiece of the NGEU.

⁷ Throughout the paper, the amounts indicated are given using 2018 prices. In current prices, the NGEU amounts to more than €800 billion.

⁸ Federico Fabbrini, *Next Generation EU. Il futuro di Europa e Italia dopo la pandemia* (Il Mulino 2022), 17; Gianluigi Bizioli, ‘Building the EU Tax Sovereignty: Lessons from Federalism’ (2022), *World Tax Journal* (WTJ), 425; Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity: Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine* (Oxford 2023).

⁹ Antonia Agulló Agüero, ‘Europa, crisis y derecho. Notas para la construcción de un nuevo derecho del gasto público’ (2016) 170, *Civitas. Revista Española de Derecho Financiero* (REDF), 39.

¹⁰ See Chapter 11 in this book: Edoardo Celeste & Goran Dominiononi, “Green & digital transition”.

3. The EU Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and its funding

3.1. *The RRF and its implementing via the National Recovery and Resilience Plans*

The centrepiece of the NGEU is the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF).¹¹ The RRF has been allocated a total amount of €672.5 billion.¹² Part of the RRF funds will go towards non-repayable grants to Member States (€312.5 billion) and the other part will be allocated to loans which will have to be repaid by the beneficiary Member States in accordance with the conditions of the original issue (a total of €360 billion).¹³

The purpose of the RRF funds is not only to contribute to Member States' recovery from the Covid-19 crisis, but also to contribute towards transformation and resilience. Therefore, they have to be transformative funds (current spending is not financed). Member States must address the structural reforms and investments needed to achieve a sustainable and resilient recovery, while promoting the EU's green and digital priorities. In order to do so, the RRF Regulation requires each Member State to adopt its National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), which must include the reforms and investments to be implemented by mid-2026, as well as the milestones and targets to be achieved, according to the timetable set.¹⁴

According to the RRF Regulation, the criteria for the assessment of the National Plans by the European Commission include the relevance of the RRP reforms and investments.¹⁵ Among other requirements, they should address the country-specific recommendations within the European Semester framework. The RRF creates a connection with the European Semester. The reforms and investments of each RRP should be tailored to the challenges identified for each country under the European Semester. Following the adoption of the RRF, the European Commission's power to steer Member States' reforms and investments towards the EU's strategic priorities and objectives has been strengthened. Pre-Covid, the recommendations in the European Semester framework were not operational, due to the lack of any incentive and sanction system¹⁶. In contrast, in order to access RRF resources, Member States have now had to

¹¹ EU Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council dated 12th February 2021 (RRF Regulation).

¹² The bulk of the NGEU funds is allocated between two financial instruments: REACT-EU (€47.5 billion) and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (€672.5 billion). *NGEU* also provides additional funding for other European programmes or funds, such as Horizon 2020, InvestEU, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the Just Transition Fund (JTF).

¹³ Article 5 of Decision 2020/2053 on the EU's own resources system. Of the total non-repayable grants, 70% are committed in 2021-2022 and 30% are committed in 2023. Loans can be subscribed until 2023; they will start to be repaid from 2028 and must be fully repaid before the end of 2058. The new net borrowing must cease by the end of 2026 at the latest.

¹⁴ See Chapter 10 in this book: Jonathan Zeitlin, David Bokhorst, and Edgars Eihmanis, "National Recovery & Resilience Plans".

¹⁵ See Chapter 14 in this book: Maria Patrin, "Decision-making: Commission & Council".

¹⁶ European Court of Auditors 'Opinion No. 6/2020 concerning the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Recovery and Resilience Facility', (COM(2020) 408), par. 45-46.

draw up their NRRP in line with the Commission's country-specific recommendations in the European Semester framework¹⁷.

Nevertheless, the EU's power to steer Member States' policies towards the EU's strategic objectives is exercised not only through the EU spending power (via RRF conditional grants), but also through the EU revenues' power (via EU new own resources), as we will see below.¹⁸ In this way, we can affirm that the EU is taking on a strategic role through its new financial legal instruments, in terms of both public expenditures and revenues.

3.2. Financing the RRF by means of the own resources system

3.2.1. The 2020 EU Own Resources Decision

As provided for in Article 311 TFEU, the EU's annual budget is financed by its own resources. The need to finance the Recovery Instrument (*Next Generation EU*) has brought about a significant change in the EU's own resources system, not only quantitatively (by increasing the amount of public revenues to be raised), but also qualitatively (by introducing new categories of own resources, which were previously non-existent).

The Union's new own resources system has been adopted by Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053/EU dated 14th December 2020 on the EU's own resource system,¹⁹ which repeals the previous Decision (EU, Euratom) 2014/335/EU of 26th May 2014.²⁰

Pursuant to Article 311 TFEU, all 27 Member States have already ratified the adoption of this new own resources Decision, in accordance with their respective constitutional requirements.

The new own resources Decision does not abolish any existing categories of own resources, but it does introduce new categories. The own resources that were already provided for in the previous Decision 2014/335/EU (and which have been maintained in Decision 2020/2053/EU with slight variations), can be briefly summarised in the following categories:

- 1) The "traditional own resources", which are mainly customs duties on imports to the EU. Member States are responsible for collecting customs duties on behalf of the

¹⁷ Hence the important impact of the RRF on the European Semester, for several reasons: 1) the RRF is fully aligned with the European Semester; 2) the RRF is a financial instrument that reinforces the European Semester; 3) the European Semester and the RRF deadlines overlap; and 4) in the coming years, the European Semester will focus on RRF management.

¹⁸ See also Christian Neumeier, 'Political Own Resources: Towards a Legal Framework' (2023), *Common Market Law Review* 60, 319.

¹⁹ OJ L 424, 15.12.2020, p. 1–10.

²⁰ OJ L 168, 7.6.2014, p. 105–111.

EU and retain, as collection costs, 25% of the revenue obtained.²¹ According to 2023 data, customs duties make up around 17% of total EU's revenues.²²

- 2) The Value Added Tax (VAT) based own resource, whereby a uniform rate of 0.30% is applied to each Member State's harmonised VAT base, which shall not exceed 50% of its Gross National Income (GNI). It should be noted that VAT is not an EU tax, but a Member State tax. According to 2023 data, this resource makes up around 16% of the EU's revenues.
- 3) The Gross National Income (GNI)-based own resource, i.e. the application of a uniform tax on the national GNI which is agreed annually. In 2023, GNI-based own resource makes up around 57% of the EU's revenues.²³

It can be seen that the concept of the EU's "own resources" is an ambiguous one. Most of the revenue from which the EU's annual budget is financed actually are national contributions from the Member States: in fact, GNI- and VAT-based resources are not genuine own resources. This is the system that has remained virtually unchanged for more than thirty years.²⁴

The main measures adopted by Decision 2020/2053/EU, and have been applicable since 1st January 2021, are as follows:

- 1) The own resources ceilings are updated. EU annual budget ceiling (the "own resources ceiling") is increased from 1.20% to 1.40% of EU's GNI for payments and to 1.46% for commitments.
- 2) It establishes the European Commission's power to borrow on the capital markets on behalf of the EU. This is a new exceptional legal-financial resource specifically designed to finance NGEU. It does not qualify as a new "own resource", as it is considered an "extraordinary and temporary complementary measure to address the crisis caused by Covid-19."²⁵
- 3) It introduces a new category of own resources: "the plastics own resource". It's a national contribution²⁶ calculated on the basis of non-recycled plastic packaging waste. This contribution is calculated by applying a uniform rate of €0.80 per

²¹ This percentage was 20% in the previous Decision 2014/335/EU and has been raised to 25% in the new Decision 2020/2053/EU on the EU's own resources system.

²² European Parliamentary Research Service, System of own resources of the European Union, September 2023, 2.

²³ The rest of the revenue that finances the Union's budget (10%) comes from a variety of other sources, including taxes on EU staff salaries and fines.

²⁴ This structure of the Union's own resources system was established by the Council Decision dated 24th June 1988 on the Community's own resources system (88/376/EEC, Euratom) and has remained virtually unchanged until the Decision 2020/2053/EU dated 14th December 2020. Previously, the EU financing system was not based on Member States' national contributions, but on traditional own resources. In this respect, see the Decision of 21st April 1970 on the replacement of financial contributions from the Member States by the Communities' own resources (70/243/ECSC, EEC, Euratom).

²⁵ Articles 2.1 and 5 of the Decision 2020/2053/UE.

²⁶ This new own resource is not set up as a tax, but as a national contribution.

kilogramme on the weight of plastic packaging waste generated in each Member State that is not recycled. It has a clear environmental purpose, consistent with the EU's strategic objectives.²⁷ The revenue from this resource is estimated at around 4% of the EU budget.²⁸

3.2.2. The roadmap for the introduction of new own resources of December 2020

Alongside the ORD Decision 2020/2053/EU, it is important to mention the Interinstitutional Agreement (IIA) dated 16th December 2020 between the EP, the Council of the EU and the European Commission regarding budgetary discipline, cooperation on budgetary matters and sound financial management, as well as new own resources, which established a legally binding “roadmap for the introduction of new own resources”. This roadmap set out the approval of new (and genuine) EU own resources within the meaning of the third paragraph of Article 311 TFEU, over the MFF period 2021-2027, in two specific stages.

The following resources were expected to be approved in 2023:²⁹

- 1) Carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM).
- 2) Resource based on the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS).
- 3) Digital services tax.³⁰

The following resources are expected to be approved by 2026:

- 1) Financial transaction tax.
- 2) Financial contribution linked to the corporate sector.
- 3) Common corporate tax base.

A number of these resources have been proposed before, without success.³¹

The resources that are making the most progress are the EU ETS and the CBAM, to which we refer below.

²⁷ Thus, as States meet these targets and reduce the generation of non-recycled plastic packaging waste, the collection of plastic packaging revenues will also be reduced.

²⁸ European Parliamentary Research Service, n. 25, 3.

²⁹ See Chapter 18 in this book: Maria Kendrick, “The Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS) and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)”. See also Chapter 19 in this book: Carlo Garbarino, “The OECD/G20 and the EU Global minimum tax”.

³⁰ The European Commission's proposals regarding the EU Digital Services Tax are now on hold as negotiations on the G20/OECD Inclusive Framework are progressing. See OECD/G20 Inclusive Framework, Multilateral Convention to Implement Amount A of Pillar One, 11 October 2023.

³¹ Among others, see the Council Decision on the EU own resources system dated 29th June 2011 (COM (2011) 510 final) and the Proposal for a Council Decision on the EU own resources system dated 2nd May 2018 (COM (2018) 325 final). For example, the Common Consolidated Corporate Tax Base (CCCTB) and the financial transaction tax were first proposed in 2011; and in 2018 the digital services tax was proposed. These proposals, which had been halted due to the unanimity rule, have been taken up again through their incorporation in the “roadmap for the introduction of new own resources” contained in the Interinstitutional Agreement dated 16th December 2020 quoted in the text.

3.2.3. The European Commission's proposals of 2021 and 2023 for the introduction of new EU's Own Resources

On 22 December 2021, the European Commission adopted a proposal for the introduction of three new revenues' sources:³² the first based on revenues deriving from an extended ETS; the second drawing on the resources generated by a CBAM; and the third based on the share (15%) of the residual profits from multinational companies that will be re-allocated to EU Member States (on the basis of Pillar One of the OECD/G20 agreement).³³ On 23 November 2022, the EP adopted a legislative resolution approving this proposal.

Regarding CBAM, on 14th July 2021 the Commission proposed a Regulation of the EP and of the Council establishing a CBAM.³⁴ It is significant that this resource is not being processed as a fiscal measure (despite its legal nature as a tax), precisely to avoid the unanimity rule provided for in the TFEU, to which we refer below. On December 2022, the Council of the EU and the EP reached a provisional agreement on the text of the EU CBAM regulation,³⁵ and the text of a directive revising the EU ETS.³⁶

Finally, the Regulation (EU) 2023/956 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 establishing a CBAM (EU CBAM Regulation) has been approved.³⁷ CBAM payments will be due from the year 2026. In 2027 CBAM payments will go to EU Member States and in 2028 part of CBAM revenues (75%) will go to the EU budget.

Regarding on the EU ETS, the Regulation (EU) 2023/957³⁸ and the Directive (EU) 2023/959³⁹ have been approved. Both legislative acts apply from 1 January 2024.

³² Proposal for a Council decision amending Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053 on the system of own resources of the European Union. COM(2021)0570.

³³ This process is complementary to the adoption of the Council Directive (EU) 2022/2523 of 14 December 2022 on ensuring a global minimum level of taxation (15%) for multinational enterprise (MNE) groups and large-scale domestic groups (DGs) within the EU ("Pillar Two directive").

³⁴ COM (2021) 564 final.

³⁵ See Council of the EU, "EU climate action: provisional agreement reached on Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)", Press release dated 13th December 2022; and European Parliament, "Deal reached on new carbon leakage instrument to raise global climate ambition", Press release dated 13th December 2022.

³⁶ See European Parliament, "Climate change: Deal on a more ambitious Emissions Trading System (ETS)", Press release dated 18th December 2022. The ETS is part of the "Fit for 55 in 2030 package".

³⁷ OJ L 130, 16.5.2023, p. 52–104.

³⁸ Regulation (EU) 2023/957 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 amending Regulation (EU) 2015/757 in order to provide for the inclusion of maritime transport activities in the EU Emissions Trading System and for the monitoring, reporting and verification of emissions of additional greenhouse gases and emissions from additional ship types (OJ L 130, 16.5.2023, p. 105–114).

³⁹ Directive (EU) 2023/959 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 amending Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and Decision (EU) 2015/1814 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading system (OJ L 130, 16.5.2023, p. 134–202).

The amounts generated by these new own resources will not be sufficient to cover all NGEU recovery repayments and borrowing costs. Therefore, the EP adopted a Resolution of 10 May 2023, 'Own Resources: A new start for EU finances. A new start for Europe'. The EP proposed the introduction of new own resources, including corporate tax-based own resources (BEFIT); the financial transaction tax (FTT); a tax on crypto-assets; and national contributions based on statistics.

On 20 June 2023, the Commission adjusted and complemented its 2021 proposal to establish new own resources for the EU budget.⁴⁰ This proposal includes adjustments to the own resources based on the ETS and the CBAM.⁴¹ In addition, the Commission proposed a new statistical own resource based on company profits. This contribution will be a national contribution paid by Member States based on the gross operating surplus for the sectors of financial and non-financial corporations. It will not be a corporate tax and it will be temporary until the “Business in Europe: Framework for Income Taxation (BEFIT)” is proposed and unanimously agreed by the EU Member States.

The revision of the ORD requires unanimity in Council (after consulting the EP) and national ratification by all Member States (in line with their constitutional requirements). Currently, the Council has yet to debate on the first and the second baskets of new own resources proposed by the Commission.

4. The Transformation of the EU’s Public Finances In Terms of Expenditures

In this section, we will analyse the impact of the RRF on two legal and financial provisions that are key in EU public expenditures, namely the Multiannual Financial Framework and the EU’s annual budget. Furthermore, we will examine the impact of the RRF on one of the budgetary cycle’s phases, i.e. the control of public spending. Finally, we will look at the impact that the RRF has on the process of reforming the budgetary discipline rules.

4.1. The impact of the Recovery and Resilience Facility on the EU Multiannual Financial Framework and on the EU Annual Budget

The Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) is the EU’s long-term budget and is regulated by Article 312 TFEU.⁴² According to the same provision, the MFF shall be established for a minimum period of five years.

The current MFF is governed by Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093 dated 17th December 2020 which establishes the MFF 2021-2027.⁴³

⁴⁰ COM/2023/331 final.

⁴¹ 30% of the revenue from auctions of ETS allowances will be allocated to the EU budget and 75% of the revenue from the mechanism will be allocated to the EU budget.

⁴² Under Article 312 of the TFEU, “the multiannual financial framework should ensure that the EU’s expenditure develops in an orderly manner and within the limits of its own resources”.

⁴³ OJ L 433I, 22.12.2020, p. 11–22.

The MFF must be respected by each EU annual budget that is approved within the relevant time period (Article 312(1) TFEU). The annual EU Budget is regulated under Articles 310 and 313-319 TFEU and Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2018/1046 of the EP and of the Council dated 18th July 2018 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (“the Financial Regulation”).

As we have already mentioned, the NGEU was specifically approved as a mechanism to reinforce the MFF 2021-2027. With its approval, the NGEU has led to a significant increase in the EU budget, not only quantitatively, but also qualitatively, in terms of the EU’s objectives and policies. Quantitatively, the MFF 2021-2027 (with €1.1 trillion), together with NGEU, almost doubles its size⁴⁴, amounting to a total of €1.8 trillion.

It should be noted that the RRF is not part of the EU Budget, because it is financed by the EU Recovery Instrument and therefore constitutes “other revenue” within the meaning of Article 311(2) TFEU.⁴⁵

4.2. The impact of the Recovery and Resilience Facility on the control of public spending

We cannot go into all the issues raised by the control of the RRF funds as they are outside the scope of this paper.⁴⁶ However, the fact remains that the RRF is a major challenge, as the European Court of Auditors has pointed out that “providing a significant amount of additional resources to be spent in a short period of time increases the pressure on control systems”⁴⁷.

The RRF (and, in particular, its implementation through the NRRPs) represents a very important change in the model for justifying spending. Both the financing and the auditing of RRF spending are linked to the effective fulfilment of the milestones and targets set out in the NRRPs. The standard model for certifying spending (eligible spending) is not followed. The RRF does not define what type of spending is eligible. Therefore, this type of auditing is new. The RRF has led to important advances with respect to the Structural Funds; in particular, we are talking about *Finance not Linked to Costs* (FLNTC), with no need for co-financing and payment in advance (no reimbursement of implemented spending), which is also almost unprecedented at EU

⁴⁴ As the European Court of Auditors (2020) points out in the above-mentioned Opinion No. 6/2020 (paragraph 16), taking into account that 60% of the non-repayable RRF grants will have to be committed in the period 2021-2022, the resources available in that period will almost double the normal MFF funding per year.

⁴⁵ This is the view of the European Court of Auditors (2020), in its Opinion No. 6/2020 (paragraph 20), that “This marks a major shift in how EU spending will be financed during the next MFF period”.

⁴⁶ See Chapter 16 in this book: Paul Dermine and Pauline Thinus, “Financial Oversight: Internal and External Control Authorities”.

⁴⁷ European Court of Auditors (2020), paragraph 23.

level.⁴⁸ In other words, the control over spending in the RRF is focused on results,⁴⁹ so that the payments and controls in the RRF are separated from the eligible spending incurred. This can lead to an improvement of the effectiveness and efficiency in public spending.

Therefore, control of RRF funds, by implementing the NRRPs, is a qualitative control, which evaluates the degree of compliance with the proposed milestones and targets, through a series of economic and social indicators.⁵⁰

Operational Arrangements are essential for the implementation of the RRF because they establish the verification mechanisms that the European Commission will use to assess whether the reforms and investments, milestones and targets have been met.⁵¹

The payment of RRF funds to Member States is linked to the effective achievement of the established milestones and targets (payments are made in tranches). According to this RRF operating system, Member States can submit payment applications twice a year, once the relevant intermediate milestones and targets agreed in the RRFs have been completed. The Commission will then assess the application within two months.

The problem is that there is no clear methodology for dealing with partial compliance of milestones and targets. Member States have different interpretations of the RRF Regulation. This raises the question of where to place the threshold for meeting milestones and, more importantly, targets, when the criteria are ambiguous. In many cases, fieldwork will be necessary in order to demonstrate that milestones and targets have been achieved. Even though the RRF is a temporary and exceptional instrument, in my opinion these issues are important not only for the RRF, but also for the future, insofar as similar financial instruments may be adopted in the coming years.

5. The Transformation of the EU's Public Finances in Terms of Revenues

As noted above, the need to finance NGEU and in particular the RRF has led to the Commission being authorised to borrow on the capital markets on behalf of the EU; the reform of the EU's own resources system; and the adoption of a roadmap for the introduction of new own resources in the future. Therefore, in this section we will focus on European public debt, as a way of obtaining extraordinary revenue to finance public

⁴⁸ See Serafin Pazos-Vidal, 'The Recovery Plan, Year Three' (2023), Agenda Pública.

⁴⁹ On monitoring and measuring performance, see European Court of Auditors (2020), paragraphs 53 to 57. In particular, in paragraph 56, it states: "the Commission should develop common indicators and set specific targets at EU level wherever possible. This would facilitate better monitoring and measurement of the implementation of the RRF at EU level, and guide Member States in using their resources more effectively to achieve EU goals. Without common indicators or the use of a common methodology, it will be difficult to monitor and audit spending, for example, on the green transition".

⁵⁰ See European Court of Auditors, 'Special report 26/2023: The Recovery and Resilience Facility's performance monitoring framework – Measuring implementation progress but not sufficient to capture performance'.

⁵¹ In this regard, see the European Commission's *Scoreboard* on Recovery and Resilience Indicators, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/business-economy-euro/recovery-coronavirus/recovery-and-resilience-facility#scoreboard>.

expenditures, with particular attention to the problems that this exceptional recourse may entail (i.e., the increase in financing costs) and the possibility of configuring public debt as a permanent own resource. Precisely, the need to finance the rising costs of EU borrowing implies the need for new and genuine own resources (new European taxes), an issue that is also analysed in this section.

5.1. European public debt

In this section, we briefly analyse the European Commission's power to borrow on the capital markets on behalf of the EU, as a new legal-financial instrument introduced by the 2020 Own Resources Decision (article 5), to finance NGEU. It should be noted that such borrowings cannot finance operational expenditure (Article 4).

Although this resource has been conceived as an extraordinary and temporary mechanism to deal with the crisis caused by Covid-19, in my opinion, it is quite possible that, in time, if its application proves successful, it will eventually be integrated into the EU's own resources system as an ordinary resource.

This is not the first time that the European Commission has borrowed on the capital markets to provide financial assistance to Member States.⁵² The first mechanism to address the European sovereign-debt crisis was the European Financial Stabilisation Mechanism (EFSM), created by Regulation (EU) No. 407/2010 of 11th May 2010,⁵³ based on Art. 122.2 TFEU.⁵⁴ More recently, we have the example of the EU's temporary Support to mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency (SURE), created by Regulation (EU) 2020/672,⁵⁵ also under Art. 122.2 TFEU.

However, there are important differences with previous experiences, both quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitatively, prior issues were limited to small amounts of borrowing, not comparable to the €750 billion authorised to finance NGEU. Qualitatively, previous European debt issuance was exclusively for lending to Member States and not for granting non-repayable grants.

This is the case of the EFSM, which allowed the Commission to borrow up to a maximum of €60 billion, in order to grant loans to States in need of financial assistance.

⁵² Ester Marco Peñas, "Derecho "en" y "tras" la pandemia. Los mecanismos de apoyo de la UE para hacer frente a la crisis de la COVID-19: el alcance de la solidaridad entre los Estados miembros de la UE", *Anuario de la Facultad de Derecho de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid*, n° extra 1, 2021, p. 353-371.

⁵³ OJ L 118, 12.5.2010, p. 1–4.

⁵⁴ Alberto de Gregorio Merino, 'Legal developments in the Economic and Monetary Union during the debt crisis: The mechanisms of financial assistance', (2012), 49, *Common Market Law Review*, Issue 5, p. 1613-1645. Other precedents are those of the temporary European Financial Stability Facility (EFSF), created in 2010, and its successor, the permanent European Stability Mechanism (ESM), created in 2012, based on Art. 136.3 TFEU, after its amendment (in these cases the debt is issued by an intergovernmental organisation).

⁵⁵ OJ L 159, 20.5.2020, p. 1–7. The SURE fund provides financial assistance in the form of EU loans to affected Member States to alleviate the socio-economic consequences of the pandemic and to cope with sudden increases in public spending in order to preserve employment.

This is also the case of the SURE, which allocated a total amount of €100 billion⁵⁶. To finance SURE, the Commission is empowered to borrow on the capital markets or from financial institutions on behalf of the EU (Article 4 of the SURE Regulation 2020/672).⁵⁷ However, unlike the RRF, the SURE fund only allows loans to be granted to Member States (no grants are available)⁵⁸ and, in addition, these loans are backed by a system of voluntary guarantees from the Member States themselves, complementing the guarantee from the EU budget⁵⁹ (Article 11 of the SURE Regulation 2020/672).

Therefore, unlike previous instruments, what is actually new in the issue of EU public debt to finance the RRF is the financing of the concessional component of NGEU (non-repayable grants) through supranational public debt.

The issuance of EU public debt to finance the NGEU is receiving a top credit rating.⁶⁰ Therefore, with this hard-won decision, the EU has become a major financial player and the role of the euro as a global currency has been strengthened.⁶¹

5.2. New European taxes: heading towards a Fiscal Union?

There is a need for long-term financing of EU public debt. Specifically, the need to finance the costs of repaying the EU's capital market borrowings which will continue until 2058. In addition, the costs for repaying the EU Recovery Instrument (EURI) borrowing costs have increased substantially. The initial amount programmed in 2021-2027 MFF (€12.9 billion in 2018 prices), was based on an interest rate for borrowing ranging from 0.55% to 1.15% for 2021-2027, while interest rates are now over 3%.⁶² The interest costs could be twice as high as initially estimated.⁶³

In order to cover NGEU funding costs exceeding the amounts initially planned in 2020, in June 2023 the Commission proposed that “a new thematic special instrument (the

⁵⁶ As of March 2022, the SURE fund was almost 90% paid out (some 90 billion euros), in the form of loans to 19 Member States.

⁵⁷ See Chapter 6 in this book: Ian Cooper, “The SURE Unemployment Reinsurance Programme”.

⁵⁸ It is worth recalling that the debt to finance the NGEU is not only used to provide loans to States (up to €360 billion), but also grants (up to €312.5 billion).

⁵⁹ In this SURE fund, each Member State's contribution to the total amount of the guarantee corresponds to its relative share of the total Gross National Income (GNI) of the EU, based on the EU budget for 2020.

⁶⁰ Daniel Alonso, Iván Kataryniuk, Carlos Moreno and Javier J. Pérez, “El programa Next Generation EU: características y claves para su éxito”, (2022), 924, *Revista Información Comercial Española*, ICE: *Revista de economía*, p. 77-97.

⁶¹ Consejo Económico y Social de España, *La gobernanza económica de la Unión Europea. El impacto de la pandemia*, Informe 03/2021 (CES, 2021).

⁶² The surge in energy prices due to Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine (in February 2022) has accelerated inflation, prompting a counter-inflationary response from the ECB and a corresponding substantial increase in interest rates. See European Parliament resolution of 10 May 2023 on the impact on the 2024 EU budget of increasing European Union Recovery Instrument borrowing costs ([2023/2037\(BUI\)](#)).

⁶³ Grégory Claeys, Conor McCaffrey and Lennard Welslau, ‘The rising cost of European Union borrowing and what to do about it’, (2023), Policy Brief 12/2023, Bruegel, p. 14.

‘EURI Instrument’) should be established, over and above the MFF ceilings, until the end of the MFF” 2021-2027.⁶⁴

To finance these costs, new resources are required. The “Own Resources” package proposed by the European Commission in June 2023 could be enough to cover these borrowing costs, if it is accepted by Member States in its current form.⁶⁵ In fact, the need to finance the rising EU borrowing costs can lead to an agreement on genuine own resources.

In particular, the need to finance the concessional component of the NGEU may provide the final impetus for the creation of new EU taxes, notably “steering taxes” (*Lenkungssteuer*). These taxes, which are predominantly for non-fiscal purposes, make it possible to analyse the resulting effect of the EU’s revenues and expenditures on the achievement of strategic objectives from a unitary view of the public finances, particularly in relation to the ecological transition and the digital transformation.⁶⁶

This demonstrates the close link between the issuance of long-term public debt and the establishment of a permanent tax system, which has historically been the case.⁶⁷

If the incorporation of these new resources becomes effective, it will lead to greater financial autonomy for the EU, reducing the dependence of the EU budget on Member States’ contributions and increasing funding through genuine own revenue.⁶⁸

However, this fiscal reform is not easy, due to, among other factors, the unanimity rule of the 27 Member States for decision-making in fiscal matters (Articles 113 and 115 TFEU). Taxation is one of the last areas of EU policy-making where decisions are taken exclusively by unanimity. Given the importance of fiscal matters in achieving EU objectives, the European Commission has proposed to move from unanimity to qualified majority voting, by means of a gradual transition. This would allow the EP to fully contribute to the formulation of EU fiscal policy and would put an end to the EU’s

⁶⁴ European Commission, ‘Proposal for a Council Regulation, amending Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093 laying down the multiannual financial framework for the years 2021 to 2027’, 2023/0201 (APP), 20 June 2023.

⁶⁵ Grégory Claeys, Conor McCaffrey and Lennard Welslau, “An estimate of the European Union’s long-term borrowing cost bill”, (2023), Policy Department for Budgetary Affairs.

⁶⁶ In this context, financing plays a key role in the construction of States’ strategic responsibility. On the one hand, financing, and in particular public financial activity, clearly contributes to the guiding or steering function (*Steuerung*) of the State. By way of example, in terms of revenues, the reinforcement of regulatory taxes can be highlighted, and in terms of expenditures, targeted subsidies. On the other hand, the State’s strategic role requires it to guarantee financing that is both inclusive and sustainable, whether it comes from the public or private sector.

⁶⁷ Thus, for example, in 1365 in Catalonia, the issuing of long-term public debt was a key element to explain the continuity of the tax system with a view to its permanence and of the General Council (“Diputación del General”) to manage it.

⁶⁸ This “would make it possible to move beyond the current nationalist logic of budget negotiations centred on the relative position of each State with respect to the budget. The division between net contributors and net beneficiaries would lose meaning in favour of a more federal logic”. See Consejo Económico y Social de España (CES, 2021).

democratic deficit.⁶⁹ While this proposal has been made before⁷⁰, in the aftermath of the Covid-19 crisis and the crisis caused by the war in Ukraine, it is considered even more necessary. Pending reform of the Treaties (a laborious and time-consuming process, since unanimity is also required), the Commission has proposed several possibilities. One possibility would be for certain fiscal proposals to be adopted through the ordinary legislative procedure, in accordance with Article 116 TFEU, although this is difficult to implement in practice. Another more feasible possibility, also proposed by the Commission, would be to use the so-called “passerelle clauses”, or “bridging clauses”, in the EU Treaties (Article 48(7) TEU and Article 192(2) TFEU).⁷¹

Recently, the EP has approved the Resolution of 22 November 2023 on proposals for the amendment of the Treaties (2022/2051(INL)).⁷²

One way or another, this reinforcement of the EP spending and revenue powers would play a key role in the "transformation" process of EU public finances that we are analysing, fulfilling the maxim “*no representation without taxation*”.

Indeed, the crisis caused by Covid-19, as Cordewener points out, is an opportunity⁷³ for EU fiscal reform.⁷⁴ The path towards fiscal autonomy in the EU has begun. But, as the scientific literature warns,⁷⁵ this road is not without obstacles. Time will tell whether the fiscal reform planned for the coming years within the EU will be successful and contribute to a qualitative leap forward in the process of European integration.⁷⁶

⁶⁹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council, “Towards more efficient and democratic decision-making in EU fiscal policy”, 15th January 2019 (COM (2019) 8 final). Somehow, institutional reform in the EU would be achieved through fiscal reform.

⁷⁰ The Commission has made this proposal on several occasions, also prior to the 2019 Communication cited in the previous footnote.

⁷¹ Proposal contained in the above-mentioned Communication, n. 61 (COM (2019) 8 final).

⁷² See Federico Fabbrini, “The European Parliament proposal for Treaty reforms”, EU Law Live, 30/11/2023.

⁷³ It is commonly asserted that crises bring progress and from crises great strategies are born.

⁷⁴ Axel Cordewener, “The COVID-19 Crisis: An Opportunity for EU Budget and Tax Reform” (2020), EC Tax Review, Vol. 29, Issue 6, 258-262. Regarding the role of tax reforms within the EU, see also Pascal Saint-Amans, “Supporting the global economy: what role for tax systems in responding to COVID-19?”, (2020), OECD; and Antonio Lanotte “The European Fiscal Support Plan in Response to COVID-19 (the Black Swan of European GDP): State Aid and Indirect Tax Measures” (2020), European Taxation, Vol. 60, n^o. 7.

⁷⁵ Gianluigi Bizioli and Edoardo Traversa, “COVID-19 and Fiscal Policies: Solidarity in the European Union in the Time of COVID-19: Paving the Way for a Genuine EU Tax?” (2020), Intertax, Vol. 48, Issue 8/9, 743-753; Ana Paula Dourado and Miguel Poiãres Maduro, “A Plead for the European Union Fiscal Autonomy” (2020), Intertax, Vol. 48, Issue 8/9, 695-697.

⁷⁶ Regardless of what happens in the future, as Alonso et. al. (2022) point out, the NGEU has already been a very important step in European integration “as it has contributed to mitigate, at least temporarily, two fundamental shortcomings of the European institutional set-up: the lack of supranational fiscal stabilisers and the relative scarcity of safe euro assets”.

6. Conclusions

Following the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020, aggravated by the Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine in 2022, EU's public finances are undergoing a series of profound quantitative and qualitative changes, in terms of both public expenditures and revenues. These changes are so far-reaching that we can speak of a real "transformation" of EU public finances. The trigger for this transformation process has been the expansionary fiscal policy adopted by the EU in the face of the Covid crisis, and especially the approval of NGEU with, as its centrepiece, the RRF.

Although these measures have been adopted on a temporary and exceptional basis in response to the Covid crisis, they have had a significant impact on the EU's classic legal-financial institutions. Firstly, the pandemic has accelerated important reforms which, although they were already in the pipeline (such as the review of European budgetary discipline and the extension of the EU's own resources system), had been stalled due to the difficulty of overcoming the unanimity rule provided for in the TFEU. This unanimity rule has always been a major obstacle for the adoption of fiscal and spending measures within the EU and thus for the advancement of the EU's financial autonomy. The need for a rapid and coordinated response to the crisis has earned the consensus of all 27 Member States. Time will tell if such consensus is also reached to implement the roadmap for the introduction of new own resources until 2026 (and, in particular, the European Commission's proposals of 2021 and 2023 for the introduction of new EU's Own Resources).

In terms of EU public expenditures, the EU spending power has clearly been strengthened. Quantitatively, because the spending that has been financed annually under the MFF has almost doubled. Qualitatively, because the Commission's power to steer Member States' actions towards achieving the EU strategic objectives has been increased (much more effectively than in the European Semester). Furthermore, the RRF has led to a change in spending control, as it does not follow the traditional justification model, but rather a *results* control model (payments are made in tranches, after monitoring the completion of milestones and targets). If the experience proves successful, it may be adopted in the future for similar financial instruments. In fact, the NGEU is already being adopted as a model for other funds. There is every reason to believe that these changes will not be limited to the MFF period 2021-2027.

In terms of the EU law of public revenues, there has also been a significant extension and reinforcement, both quantitatively and qualitatively, of the EU's revenue power, through the reform of the EU's own resources system, which affects both traditional and new resources. To finance NGEU, the European Commission has resorted to borrowing on the capital markets. Unlike previous instruments (such as SURE, also financed by debt), financing the RRF with European debt is not only intended to provide loans to States (which they will have to repay on the same terms as the original issue), but also grants. Thus, this debt issuance is a first in EU history. Meanwhile, in order to finance the costs of repaying the principal and interest payments on this European public debt, a new category of own resources has been approved and a roadmap for the introduction of new own resources in the future (until 2026) has been established. The European

Commission has approved two proposals, of 2021 and 2023, for the introduction of new EU's Own Resources. The need to finance European public debt expenditure in the long term (until 2058) has been the catalyst for promoting a system of genuine own resources with a long-term approach to ensure the financial sufficiency, sustainability and financial autonomy of the Union.⁷⁷

Time will tell whether the process of transforming EU public finances described in this chapter (which to date has already led to significant progress on both the expenditures and revenues sides of EU public finances) will be consolidated in the future and allow progress to be made in the European integration process. The NGEU could be the blueprint for the creation of permanent European fiscal instruments. We are in a pivotal moment, where the path towards EU fiscal autonomy could lead to structural reform. There are important obstacles on this path, in particular the unanimity rule of the 27 Member States regarding the adoption of fiscal decisions within the EU. In this respect, the Commission already made proposals in 2019 to progressively move from unanimity to qualified majority voting. This would strengthen the Union's fiscal power and Parliament's role in decision-making. It is not an easy path, but this is also the direction in which recent proposals to reform the EU Treaties to extend the Union's competences are heading.⁷⁸

In short, in the current situation, facing the sustainability crisis triggered by the Great Recession of 2008 and accentuated by the Covid-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, financing is not only a tool to help fulfil the functions of the EU and the States, but also a real driver of transformation of public finances and institutions, both European and national. In the face of such a transformation, a continuous revision of the fundamental legal categories is required. Moreover, future challenges require a coordinated response (at global, EU and national level), as well as cooperation between all the different sectors (public and private), in order to achieve the objectives that are considered strategic for the 21st century.⁷⁹ Globalisation and digitalisation have created common challenges that require common solutions⁸⁰. Strengthening the EU's fiscal autonomy, in terms of both revenue and expenditures, in order to meet collective needs (genuine EU public goods), will not only help to advance the European integration process, but it will also contribute to the definition and achievement of the EU's strategic objectives.

⁷⁷ Although NGEU is an off-budget instrument, the payment of interest rates is part of the current EU budget and the actual repayment of this borrowing will be part of the EU budget from 2027 onwards. See European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS), System of own resources of the European Union, September 2023, 3-4.

⁷⁸ In this respect, see the Conference on the Future of Europe (Report on the final outcome, May 2022) and the European Parliament Resolution dated 6th June 2022 on the call for a convention on the revision of the Treaties. See also the Resolution of 22 November 2023 on proposals of the EP for the amendment of the Treaties (2022/2051(INL)).

⁷⁹ Among others, the NGEU itself; the Commission's *Fit for 55* package and the SDGs of the UN Agenda 2030.

⁸⁰ COM (2019) 8 final.